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TA'LIM JARAYONIGA AN'ANAVIY VA ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUV

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“Iqtisodiyot va pedagogika universiteti” nodavlat ta'lim muassasasi “Kompyuter tizimlari” kafedrasida o'qituvchisi

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“Iqtisodiyot va pedagogika universiteti” nodavlat ta'lim muassasasi talabasi

ANNOTATSIYA

O'quv jarayonida zamonaviy innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish shartlari to'g'risida fikr-mulohazalar bildirildi. O'quv jarayoni samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ba'zi masalalari muhokama qilingan. Maqolada O'zbekiston ilm-fanni yanada rivojlantirishning zamonaviy jihatlari, chuqur bilim, yuksak ma'naviyatli va madaniyatli yoshlarni tarbiyalash, iqtisodiyotni shakllantirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan raqobatbardosh samarali foydalanish va bu sohada kadrlar tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

***Kalit so'zlar:** kompyuter, internet, ilova, kompetentsiya, ta'lim texnologiyalari.*

ТРАДИЦИОННЫЙ И СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ПОДХОД К ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМУ ПРОЦЕССУ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья из журнала "Современные инновационные технологии в образовательном процессе" дана обратная связь по условиям использования. В статье из журнала "Инновационные технологии в повышении эффективности образовательного процесса" обсуждались некоторые вопросы использования. В статье рассматриваются современные аспекты дальнейшего развития науки в Узбекистане, глубокие знания, высокая образованность молодежи, духовность и культура, конкурентоспособное эффективное использование цифровых технологий при формировании экономики и уделяется особое внимание подготовке кадров в этой сфере.

Ключевые слова: компьютер, интернет, приложение, компетентность, образовательная технология.

TRADITIONAL AND MODERN APPROACH TO EDUCATION PROCESS**Sa'dullayev Avaz Akmal o'g'li**

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ABSTRACT

Article from modern innovative technologies in the educational process feedback has been made on the conditions of use. In the article from innovative technologies in improving the efficiency of the educational process some issues of use have been discussed. In The Article Uzbekistan modern aspects of the further development of Science, Deep Knowledge, high educating young people with spirituality and culture, competitive effective use of digital technologies in the formation of the economy and it pays special attention to the training of personnel in this area.

Key words: *computer, internet, application, competence, educational technology.*

What is the difference between the traditional method of education, and today's more progressive approach?

The Traditional Approach - Traditionally, teachers were seen as vehicles to provide students with information and facts. Teachers stood at the front of the classroom and imparted information for the students to absorb. Teachers acted as 'gate-keepers' of information and decided what to teach the children and what to omit. The goal was to prepare the student for life outside the classroom by supplying the knowledge they would need for university and beyond. In this model, there is not much concern for the students themselves and their individuality or creativity. The focus is more on moulding the student into an educated, ethical, constructive and hard-working member of society once they join the work-force. In this particular model, the teacher is at the centre, while the students are on the periphery.

The Progressive Approach - Conversely, the modern approach, otherwise known as the progressive approach, places the student at the centre of the model. Schools who adopt the progressive approach are excited by the idea of student's curiosity and aim to instill a love of learning about all things – not just a curriculum. The idea behind this model of education is to foster independent thinking. - Teachers who use this model reward students for asking questions and encourage inquisitiveness

and self-study. While they go about the business of preparing students for their academic goals, progressive teachers will tailor their lessons to meet the unique needs of their students, thereby making the coursework more interesting and creating an environment of joy around learning instead of fear or obligation.

Which Approach Do We Adopt at ME? - While there are benefits and challenges to both models of education, at ME, we adopt a more progressive approach. On our website, you will find our mission – it reads:

"At ME our top priority is always the student. We treat our students like family, investing in them long-term, with many students staying with us from primary school all the way to grade 12. With small group classes and private lessons, we will cater our lessons to the needs of our students to help them reach their academic goals."

Why Do We Adopt a Progressive Approach? - We want our students to be lifelong learners, with a thirst for knowledge and the ability to find answers themselves. We want our students to continuously engage with new ideas and find new ways of solving problems. We do this by recognising and honouring the creativity and passions of our individual students.

Our teachers don't feed the students facts and figures and expect them to be memorised and regurgitated. We encourage hands-on, interactive learning through projects, experiments, and teamwork. At ME, one of our greatest successes is when a student is able to identify a passion and together, we work on ways to pursue it. We believe that this model allows students to develop a love for education. We encourage our students to use critical thinking skills outside the classroom as they evaluate their opinions on real-world topics and issues.

What About Discipline and Curriculums? We understand that some students do better with a more authoritarian style of teaching and for these students, we cater accordingly. There is a difference between progressive education and lessons that are a "free-for-all" While encouraging students to question, have fun and enjoy their course-work, our teachers are also ensuring that there is still discipline and order in the classroom. The one does not negate the other.

Because our courses specialise in academic tuition for students following international and local curricula, we still have strict aims and guidelines to meet. While we encourage interesting discussion, we also maintain high standards and ensure standardised test preparation & educational planning objectives are always met.

In Conclusion - When it comes to the discussion of traditional vs. progressive teaching models, we believe students learn better with hands-on, experiential learning. Progressive education focuses on what students are passionate about and what critical thinking skills they can develop within the classroom framework and beyond. We also believe that progressive education truly benefits our students in the long run and gives them a passion and excitement around learning. A society that continually learns, is one that will evolve and go from strength-to-strength. As the old saying goes, "never stop learning, because life never stops teaching."

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